

Riemann's "Functional" Equation is Not Valid and its Implication on the Riemann Hypothesis

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ABSTRACT

Riemann's "functional" equation was formulated by Bernhard Riemann in his 1859 paper[1]. If it is valid, then a real function is obtained that has zeros similar to the hypothesized zeros of the Riemann zeta function.

The **Riemann Hypothesis** states that 'all the nontrivial zeros of the zeta function are at $z = \frac{1}{2} + yi$ '. Thus, the Riemann's "functional" equation *is* the foundation upon which the Riemann Hypothesis is based. But the "functional" equation, as shall be shown here, is not valid such that the Riemann Hypothesis crumbles on its claim.

Introduction

The Riemann zeta constant is shown below

$$(1) \quad \zeta\{s\} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \quad \Re(s) > 1, s = \sigma + \omega i$$

Where n is the independent variable while $s (= \sigma + \omega i)$ is a complex constant with real part σ and imaginary part ω , and i is the imaginary unit $i = \sqrt{-1}$. $\zeta\{s\}$ is constant since we are taking the sum for all values of n , and the real part of the single-valued s must be greater than 1 such that (1) converges.

Consider the widely known Riemann's "functional" equation

$$(2) \quad \zeta\{s\} = 2^s \pi^{s-1} \sin\left\{\frac{\pi s}{2}\right\} \Gamma\{1-s\} \zeta\{1-s\}.$$

The series (1) absolutely converges if $\sigma > 1$ while the right-side of (2) converges if $\sigma < 0$. Thus, (1) and (2) don't have common values that would make them equal so that

$$\zeta\{s\} \neq 2^s \pi^{s-1} \sin\left\{\frac{\pi s}{2}\right\} \Gamma\{1-s\} \zeta\{1-s\},$$

which proves that (2) is **not** a valid equation.

Riemann obtained (2) from the contour integral

$$I\{s\} = \int_C \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz,$$

and also

$$(3) \quad \zeta\{s\} = -\frac{\Gamma\{1-s\}}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(-x)^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx,$$

which is widely accepted as the "analytic continuation" of $\zeta\{s\}$ for all s except at $s = 1$. I will show next that

$$\zeta\{s\} \neq -\frac{\Gamma\{1-s\}}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(-x)^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx,$$

or (3) is **not** a valid equation.

Riemann's "Functional" Equation Is Not Valid

If $x > 0$,

$$\frac{1}{e^z - 1} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-nz}$$

and

$$I\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \int_{+\infty}^{+\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-nz} (z)^{s-1} dz$$

Let $w = nz$, $dw = ndz$

$$I\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \int_{+\infty}^{+\infty} w^{s-1} e^{-w} dw$$

The contour integral of $I\{s\}$ if $z = x$ and x going from $+\infty$ and back again to $+\infty$ is

$$I_1\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \int_{\infty}^{\infty} x^{s-1} e^{-x} dx = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \left\{ \int_{\infty}^0 e^{-x} x^{s-1} dx + \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{s-1} dx \right\}$$

$$I_1\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \{-\Gamma\{s\} + \Gamma\{s\}\} = 0 \quad \sigma > 1, s = s.$$

Because $I_1\{s\} = 0$,

$$I_1\{s\} = 0 \neq -2i \sin\{\pi s\} \zeta\{s\} \Gamma\{s\}$$

and so

$$\zeta\{s\} \neq -\frac{\Gamma\{1-s\}}{2\pi i} \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(-x)^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx \neq -\left\{ \frac{\Gamma\{1-s\}}{2\pi i} (0) = 0 \right\}.$$

Therefore, (3) is **not** a valid equation.

The Misapplication of the Residue Theorem

Riemann applied the Residue Theorem on (4) by assuming the quantities $2\pi ni$ for $n = \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3$, and so on, as the poles of (4). The function $q(z) = 1/(e^z - 1)$ in (4) is a periodic function of z ,

$$q(z + 2\pi i) = \frac{1}{e^{(z+2\pi i)} - 1} = \frac{1}{e^z - 1} \quad z \neq 0,$$

since the exponential function e^z is a periodic function with period $2\pi i$. Hence the term $2\pi ni$ are the multiple of the *fundamental period* $2\pi i$. It is, therefore, not valid to treat them as the poles of (6). In fact, the only pole of $q(z)$ is at $z = 0$ with residue 1,

$$\oint \frac{dz}{e^z - 1} = 2\pi i.$$

Unfortunately, one can not use $z = 0$ on $I\{s\}$ because it will be undefined

$$\begin{aligned} \int_C \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz &= (0)^{s-1} - 2\pi i \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-2\pi ni)^{s-1} + (2\pi ni)^{s-1} \right) = \text{undefined} \\ &= \text{undefined} \neq -2\pi i \sin\left\{\frac{\pi s}{2}\right\} 2^s \pi^{s-1} \zeta\{1-s\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the integral on this contour is **not** valid.

Or consider the contour integral ($a > 0$)

$$I_2\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \int_C \frac{z^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = (-1)^{s-1} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{1}{n^s} \int_{a-\infty i}^{a+\infty i} w^{s-1} e^{-w} dw \right\} = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \int_{a-\infty i}^{a+\infty i} w^{s-1} e^{-w} dw$$

$$M = \left| (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \int_{a-\infty i}^{a+\infty i} w^{s-1} e^{-w} dw \right| = |\zeta\{s\}| e^{-a} R^{\sigma-1} \quad \text{and} \quad L = \int_{a-\infty i}^{a+\infty i} |z'(\tau)| d\tau = 2R$$

$$ML = \lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} 2 e^{-a} |\zeta\{s\}| R^{\sigma} = \begin{cases} \infty & \sigma > 1 \\ \text{indeterminate} & \sigma < 0 \end{cases}$$

As you can see that if $-\infty < y < +\infty$, the resulting contour integral is indeterminate.

Also, if $x < 0$

$$I\{s\} = -(-1)^{s-1} \int_C \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} e^{nz} (z)^{s-1} dz = (-1)^s \int_C \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} z^{s-1} e^z dz = (-1)^s \int_{-\infty}^0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} z^{s-1} e^z dz = \text{undefined}.$$

Thus, if we want a $I\{s\}$ to be finite (as R approaches ∞), x must be greater than zero ($x > 0$) or $0 < |z| < 2\pi$ (see Appendix).

CONCLUSION

Therefore, since Riemann's functional equation is not valid, it follows that the Riemann hypothesis is also not valid.

Appendix

Some Contour Integrals of $I(s)$

Let us now look closely at $I\{s\}$,

$$(4) \quad I\{s\} = \int_C \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = \begin{cases} I\{s\} & s = s \\ 0 & \text{not } s \end{cases} .$$

The integral $I\{s\}$ depends on s , the endpoints z_1 and z_2 , and the chosen path itself. Where $z (= x + yi)$ is the independent variable and $s (= \sigma + ti)$ is a complex constant.

Since s is constant, Δs and ΔI are both zero. So that

$$\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta s} = \frac{0}{0} = \text{indeterminate} \quad \text{and} \quad \int_s^s I\{s\} ds = 0, .$$

Since both $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta s}$ and $\frac{dI}{ds}$ do not exist, which proves that $I\{s\}$ is *not* a function.

its role is to ensure that $I\{s\}$ is finite for a given value of s ($|I\{s\}| < \infty$),

$$|I\{s\}| = \left| \int_C \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz \right| < M L < \infty$$

where

$$M = \left| \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} \right| \quad \text{and} \quad L = \int_a^b |z'(\tau)| d\tau .$$

Note: $(-1)^{s-1}$ is simply a multi-valued complex quantity with principal values

$$(-1)^{-1}(-1)^s = -e^{\pm(\pi is)} .$$

If $x > 0$,

$$I\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \int_{+\infty}^{+\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-nz} (z)^{s-1} dz = (-1)^{s-1} \int_{+\infty}^{+\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} z^{s-1} e^{-z} dz$$

$$I\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \int_{+\infty}^{+\infty} z^{s-1} e^{-z} dz \quad \sigma > 1$$

- Path C_1 : $z = x$, x from $+\infty$ to 0 and from 0 to $+\infty$

$$I_1\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \int_{\infty}^0 x^{s-1} e^{-x} dx + \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{s-1} dx$$

$$I_1\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \{-\Gamma\{s\} + \Gamma\{s\}\} = 0 \quad \sigma > 1, s=s$$

- Path C_2 : $z = x$, $0 < x < \infty$

$$I_2\{s\} = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{s-1} dx = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \Gamma\{s\} \quad \sigma > 1, s=s$$

- Path C_3 : $z = a + yi$, for constant $a > 0$ and $-\infty < y < +\infty$

$$I_3\{s\} = \int_C \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = (-1)^{s-1} \int_C \frac{z^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = (-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\} \int_{a-\infty i}^{a+\infty i} z^{s-1} e^{-z} dz$$

$$M = |(-1)^{s-1} \zeta\{s\}| |(a+\infty i)^{s-1} e^{-(a+\infty i)}| = |\zeta\{s\}| R^{\sigma-1} e^{-a} \quad \text{and} \quad L = \int_{a-\infty i}^{a+\infty i} |z'(\tau)| d\tau = 2R$$

$$ML = \lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} 2 |\zeta\{s\}| R^{\sigma} e^{-a} = \begin{cases} \infty & \sigma > 1 \\ \text{indeterminate} & \sigma < 0 \end{cases}$$

If $x < 0$,

$$I\{s\} = -(-1)^{s-1} \int_C \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} e^{nz} (z)^{s-1} dz = (-1)^s \int_C \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} z^{s-1} e^z dz = (-1)^s \int_C \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} z^{s-1} e^z dz = \text{undefined}$$

- Path C_4 : $z = x$, $-\infty < x < 0$

$$I_4\{s\} = \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{(-x)^{s-1}}{e^x - 1} dx = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{s-1}}{e^{-x} - 1} dx = - \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} e^{-nx} x^{s-1} dx = - \left\{ \zeta\{s\} \Gamma\{s\} + \left(\int_0^{\infty} x^{s-1} dx = \infty \right) \right\} = -\infty$$

Circular path: $z = r e^{i\theta} \quad 0 < r < 2\pi$

$$\frac{z}{e^z - 1} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m z^m}{m!}$$

where B_m are the Bernoulli numbers,

$B_0 = 1, B_1 = -1/2, B_2 = 1/6, B_3 = 0, B_4 = -1/30, B_5 = 0, B_6 = 1/42, B_7 = 0, B_8 = -1/30, B_9 = 0$, etc.

$$I\{s\} = \int_r^{re^{2\pi i}} \frac{(-z)^{s-1}}{e^z - 1} dz = \int_r^{re^{2\pi i}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m z^m}{m!} (-1)^{s-1} z^{s-1} \frac{dz}{z} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m}{m!} (-1)^{s-1} \int_r^{re^{2\pi i}} z^{m+s-1} \frac{dz}{z}$$

For complex s

$$I\{s\} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m}{m!} (-1)^{s-1} \int_r^{re^{2\pi i}} z^{m+s-1} \frac{dz}{z} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m}{m!} (-1)^{s-1} r^{(m+s-1)} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{(m+s-1)i\theta} i d\theta$$

$$I\{s\} = -2i \sin\{\pi s\} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m r^{m+s-1}}{m!(m+s-1)} \quad s=s$$

When $s = -n$ ($n = 0$, or 1 , or $2, \dots$),

$$I\{-n\} = \int_r^{re^{2\pi i}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m}{m!} (-1)^{-n-1} z^{m-n-1} \frac{dz}{z} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m}{m!} (-1)^{-n-1} \int_0^{2\pi} z^{m-n-1} i d\theta$$

$$I\{-n\} = 2\pi i \frac{B_{n+1}}{(n+1)!} (-1)^{-n-1}$$

When $s = 1$

$$I(1) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m}{m!} \int_0^{2\pi} z^m i d\theta = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m}{m!} r^m \int_0^{2\pi} e^{mi\theta} i d\theta = 2\pi i$$

When $s = n$ ($n = 2$, or 3 , or $4, \dots$),

$$I\{n\} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m}{m!} (-1)^{n-1} \int_r^{re^{2\pi i}} z^{m+n-2} dz = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_m}{m!} (-1)^{n-1} r^{(m+n-1)} \int_0^{2\pi} e^{(m+n-1)i\theta} i d\theta = 0$$

REFERENCES

- [1] Riemann, Bernhard (1859). *On the Number of Prime Numbers less than a Given Magnitude*.
- [2] Brown, James Ward; Churchill, Ruel V. (1996). *Complex Variables and Applications* (6th ed.). Singapore: McGraw Hill International Editions.

LINKS

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Riemann_zeta_function
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Riemann_hypothesis